

Material Name	Material Type (Format)	Description	URL/Persistent Identifier
Where to go when your bioinformatics outgrows your compute - slides	Slides (PDF and PPTX)	Slides presented during the webinar	Included in this Zenodo record
Where to go when your bioinformatics outgrows your compute	Recording (YouTube video)	Recording of the live webinar presentation	Available on the Australian BioCommons YouTube channel https://youtu.be/hNTbngSc-W0
Australian research computing resources cheat sheet	Handout (PDF)	A list of resources and useful links mentioned during the webinar.	Included in this Zenodo record